

Not Yet Uhuru: Irene Salami's *Emotanas* a Paradigm in the Leadership Question in Nigeria

David Essi

University of Calabar, Calabar - Nigeria

Corruption is the cancerous bane forestalling the growth and development of the Nigerian nation right from independence till date and the political cabal have apotheosized corruption and made the fight against prebendalistic graft and corruption antediluvian history (Bobson Gbinije "2015: Corruption: Jonathan and the tenacity of Power". 19).

Abstract:

Over the years, Nigerian leaders have shown by their actions and inactions that rather than being "fathers", they have been political demagogues with an inexorable appetite for kleptomania. This accounts for why the development of the country has been one of motion without movement. This paper examines the practice of Democracy in Nigeria and how our leaders have fared since independence as well as the dogged activities of playwrights as social vanguards protecting, the "social mandate" Irene Salami's *Emotan* is x-rayed in this discourse as a paradigm. This writer submits that Nigeria as a nation since inception, is bereft of "fathers" with a genuine desire to do the greatest good for the greatest number of the citizenry.

Keywords: Democracy, Demagogues, Corruption, Selfless Service, Revolution.

Résumé

Au fil des années, les dirigeants nigériens ont démontré par leurs actions et leurs inactions que, plutôt que d'être des « pères », ils ont été des démagogues politiques avec un appétit inexorable pour la kleptomanie. Cela explique pourquoi le développement du pays a été une motion sans mouvement. Cet article examine la pratique de la démocratie au Nigeria et la façon dont nos dirigeants se débrouillent depuis l'indépendance, ainsi que les activités engagées des dramaturges en tant que protecteurs sociaux, qui protègent le « mandat social ». *Emotan* d'Irène Salami est radiographié dans ce discours comme un paradigme. Cet auteur admet que le Nigeria en tant que nation depuis sa création, est privé de « pères » avec un véritable désir de faire le plus grand bien pour le plus grand nombre des citoyens.

Mots-clés : Démocratie, Démagogues, corruption, altruisme, révolution

Introduction.

...When you see that men get richer by graft and by pull them by work, and your laws don't protect you against them, but protect them against you, when you see corruption being rewarded and honesty becoming a self sacrifice, you may know that your society is doomed (Ayn Rand atlas Shrugged 68)

Democracy which comes from a combination of two Greek words – demos (which means the body of citizens living within a particular city – state); and Kratos (which means power or rule). Democracy thus meant rule by the people or the many – the direct personal participation of the citizen in the government of the city. Thus, from the ancient Greek era to today’s America, now touted as the world’s democratic model, the practice and application of democratic cannons in establishing socio-political issues have become the deciding indicators in judging the occidental and the developing societies. Today, Nigeria is almost at the threshold of two decades into its fourth republic, as such, the application of democratic norms or otherwise in the running of the affairs politically in Nigeria becomes relevant if we must make meaningful progress.

Human societies all over the world have developed some minimum acceptable standards to regulate and ensure the smooth running of these societies. These minimum standards are what could be referred to as laws and certain individuals invariably become its guardians. Writers and human right activists are generally seen as natural guardians of the law. Human history is replete with names like Aristophanes, Socrates, Bertolt Brecht, William Shakespeare, John Sheridan, Ken Saro Wiwa, Wole Soyinka, Chinua Achebe, Martin Luther King Jr. Desmond Tutu, NgugiWa Thiong O, Dai Lama and others are quite notable. Some of these individuals mentioned above have had to cool their heels in prison because of constant clashes with the powers that be who are intolerant of the views of the opposition.

From Paul Biya’s Cameroon, Al Bashir’s Sudan, to Yoweri Museveni’s Uganda and ousted Robert Mugabe of Zimbabwe, African leaders have shown by their actions that they are intolerant of the views of the opposition. This brings to bear the view of Francis Fukuyama that “most leaders are Megalothymic” (130). In reprimanding our leaders vaulting ambition to ascend to power at all cost as well as silencing all perceived opposition, Femi Osofisan reports:

KANSILOR: The law is a chameleon: It adjusts its coat always
to the colour of strength

BAALE: There is only one law. You swore to defend it!

KANSILOR: My oath Baale, is to serve the people using the law as a
weapon. But if the law itself stand in the way of my
service, the law must yield! (*Aringindin and the
Nightwatchmen* 75)

Leaders who trample on justice and make the law to succumb to their selfish ambition are no leaders. This is what Kansilor exhibits in his inordinate ambition; how the law could be made to yield to the vaulting ambition of an individual. In Nigeria, the record of human rights abuse is quite humongous. The government and its officials are quite “above the law”. They give no regard to the constituted authority or to any law. Law court injunctions are barely respected by our leaders. However, the laws are made to check the outbursts of the masses by the rich and powerful.

This paper examines the practice of democracy in the Nigerian national space as well as the quest for an ideal leadership using Irene Salami's *Emotan*. This is because those we have been unfortunate to have as leaders were no better than egomaniacs and Megalothymics, using the words of Francis Fukuyama.

Democracy: The Nigerian Experience

Nigeria obtained her independence from colonial Britain on 1st October, 1960 without any armed struggle on the part of Nigeria. Thereafter, Nigeria practiced the parliamentary system of government fashioned after British model. This saw the three (3) regions into which Nigeria was divided (North, West and Eastern regions) being run as semi-autonomous regions with each region at liberty to develop as it pleased. However, this political dispensation was short-lived as bickering and financial recklessness soon brought the soldiers out of their barracks into governance. This military misadventure, so it seemed, saw Nigeria going through a 30 month long war with its attendant socio-economic consequences.

After the failure of the First Republic, the Second Republic took off in 1979 fashioned after the America presidential system of government. This presidential system of government touted as a federal system of government has seen the centre – the federal government wielding so much power. The irresponsibility of our Second Republic leaders saw the coming of the soldiers once again to abort this democratic process. With so many shifts in dates, the third republic presidential election that was believed to have been won in a free and fair contest by Late Chief M.K.O Abiola was annulled by Nigeria's self-styled President Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida. In the miasma of this political debacle, late General Sani Abacha took over the reins of power in a palace coup and took Nigeria down a political cul-de-sac until his untimely death ended this political rigmorole. General Abdulsalam Abubakar who took over started his own transition programme and ended up foisting General Olusegun Obasanjo (Rtd) on Nigerians, in what became the Fourth Republic.

Obasanjo's eight years as civilian ruler could best be described as eight years of a maximum leader. Upon the expiration of his two tenures of four years each, Obasanjo fruitlessly sought for a tenure elongation. With the failure of his tenure elongation bid, Obasanjo supported Late Umaru Musa Yar'Adua in the 2007 "do or die" presidential election (according to Obasanjo) to succeed him. Late Umaru Musa Yar'Adua won the election but died midway into his tenure. Late President Umaru Musa Yar'Adua was succeeded by President Goodluck Jonathan who was hitherto his (Yar'Adua's) Vice President. President Goodluck Jonathan completed his late principal's tenure, contested and won a fresh mandate in 2011. President Goodluck Jonathan, a man from the Niger-Delta region of Nigeria, failed against all expectations to meet the yearnings and aspirations of Nigerians. His tenure witnessed thievery of gargantuan dimension by his appointed ministers and aides. This makes Bobson Gbinije to claim that "the level of corruption and lack of transparency in the Jonathan administration is so proverbially unprecedented that it cannot be wished away" (19). President Goodluck Jonathan at best could be described as a sitting duck during his tenure. He failed woefully in his re-election bid in 2015. His party the PDP (People's Democratic Party) was trounced in the 2015 presidential election by the

APC (All Progressives Congress) which had President Muhammadu Buhari as its presidential candidate.

President Mohammadu Buhari who won the 2015 presidential election came into power with his “Change” mantra vowing to clean the Augean stable of corruption, ineptitude and fiscal irresponsibility of the hitherto PDP government. From all indications, the eighteen years of democracy so far witnessed in this Fourth republic has been a most trying period for Nigeria and Nigerians. Right from time, artists in the cloak of moral agents have been in the forefront of the demand for change. It is in the light of the “mandate” which could be referred to as “sacred mandate” which artists are seen to be holding as watchdogs of every society that we examine. *Emotan* by Irene Salami, written on the Nigerian situation.

Emotan as a moral thesis on the Nigerian Leadership.

A writer in one of Nigerian dailies made this declaration:

The problem of Nigeria is that of fatherlessness, Nigeria as a nation has never been fathered. Check every nation that has grown to any level of greatness and development economically, socially and politically, you will discover that there are men that have actually fathered such nations. Some even sacrifice their lives on the altar of nationalism for their nation... men like Abraham Lincoln, George Washington, Winston Churchill, Mahatma Gandhi, Mao Tse Tung, Charles de Gaulle and Ben Gurion. Back to Africa, you have Nelson Mandela, Kwame Nkrumah, Julius Nyerere... these are men that had served their nations selflessly with the vision of nurturing their nations to greatness. As I check through history, I ask myself the question, who are the fathers of Nigeria as a nation? ...Nigeria is a nation born out of due time by immature parents, midwived by highly inexperienced nurses,... till today, we are one but not a whole, we are jointed but not linked..., the cry of my heart for Nigeria is “Lord, give us fathers! Fathers with a vision. Fathers with a passion for the nation, fathers that will nurture , sustain, protect, teach, lead by example, discipline with love, care for and develop this fatherless nation called Nigeria (Aiyedogbon 20)

It is indeed a sad trajectory that for more than five decades of Nigeria’s independence, the country has been in political and leadership doldrums as Chinua Achebe claim thus:

...The whole trouble with Nigeria rests squarely on leadership and Nigeria is less than fortunate with her leaders (13)

Many Nigerian playwrights and scholars have consistently pre-occupied themselves thematically with the search for an ideal leader or leadership. It is in this regard that Ola Rotimi expresses his own view on the personality of an ideal leader. He says:

First, my ideal leader must be a man or woman who is unreservedly detribalized. Only in this state can that leader’s judgment subordinate bias to principles. Second, the person must be

committed to the well being of the generality of his people which means that he/she must be selfless. Third, that person must be action-bound. Fourth, the person must be forthright in the pursuit of fairness as in the dispensation of justice.. (21)

Bobson Gbinije, in his reference to Richard Nixon's Profile and reminiscences of men who have shaped the modern world reports.

Great leadership is a form of art, requiring both force and vision to an extraordinary degree, the leader necessarily deals to a large extent in symbols, in images and sort of galvanizing idea that both persuade and move them. The manager thinks of today and tomorrow but the leader thinks of the day after tomorrow. The leader represents a direction of history (19)

Emotan by Irene Salami aptly captures Nigeria's brand of leadership demonstrated by the insensitivity of the ruling class and their fondness for holding on to power, decimating all opposition and perceived enemies as well as amassing wealth at the expense of the ruled. The play presents before our very eyes the contemporary political realities in Nigeria serving therefore as a moral thesis and a critique of the idiosyncrasies of the ruling class (leaders). The play –*Emotan* opens with a coterie of self—centred chiefs cruelly plotting the downfall of a would—be Oba (Ogun). Chief Iyase, the prime minister's speech attests to this:

IYASE: Our strategy will be to convince him to banish Ogun from the kingdom (5).

With superior argument and blackmail, the chiefs successfully cajole Oba Orobiru into banishing his brother (the right heir to the throne) to the evil forest and never to set foot on the soil of Benin Kingdom again.

OKOBIRU: Enough of your savoury words. I have decided that you leave the kingdom of Benin at once. You are barnished out of the kingdom of Benin at once. You are banished out of this kingdom for as long as I remain on the throne. My guards will take you to Unuame on the Ovia River... Any day you ever set foot on the soil of Benin kingdom, while I am seated on this throne, you will become a dead man. Do you understand? A dead man I say, Ogun (10).

This corruption and injustice continues as Irughe (Ogun's younger brother) who accompanies him in exile usurps the throne. Irughe takes the title of Oba Uwafiokun. Much later, it is discovered that *Emotan* is the brain behind Ogun's efforts to regain the throne. Several plans are made to thwart *Emotan*'s efforts including a plot to marry her into the Oba's harem.

IHAMA: She is a very pretty woman. She has never had any child. If you ask my opinion, I think you should "bae igban" and put

her in your harem. Let her become one of your numerous wives under the care of your “Eson”. She will in no time be engaged in domestic trivialities. I feel this is a better plan than asking an army to go seek mere Emotan. It will be like using a cutlass to kill an ant. (22)

Focused and determined as she is, Emotan refuses to be grounded in whatever form including the royal privilege of becoming a queen. She responds thus:

EMOTAN: I would rather die than become a queen in Oba Uwafiokun’s harem, the usurper, the traitor, the schemer. I would rather die, you can take my corpse to him when I am dead (30-31)

In the play, Ogun’s younger brother who usurped the throne taking the title of Uwafiokun is prodded on by the advisers. These advisers are charlatans and sycophants. Over the years in Nigeria, charlatan and sycophantic advisers have been the bane of ideal leadership. These advisers have a way of surfacing in every successive government since independence in Nigeria. Iyase’s speech corroborates this assertion.

IYASE: We congratulate your majesty for your successful ascension to the throne of Benin. We assure you of our continued support and loyalty. Oba Ugha to Okpere (13).

Former military president Ibrahim Babangida was wrongly advised to annul the 1993 presidential election believed to have been won by late Chief M.K.O Abiola. Late General Sani Abacha who took over from General Babangida was equally advised by his cronies to transmute into a civilian president. In 2006, chief Olusegun Obasanjo, the then president was equally advised to contest for a third term in office.

A power drunk leadership that seeks to hunt down perceived opposition is what we find in *Emotan*. Oba Uwafiokun seeks to haunt Emotan whom he sees as a threat. He says to Isoken, his queen

UWA: I am in control, I am disturbed no doubt but I am still in control. I can handle Emotan myself, I will deal with her personally (36)

Under President Olusegun Obasanjo’s tenure, Nigerians lived in a siege as all perceived opposition was clamped on. A state of emergency was declared in Plateau and Ekiti States.

Prince Ogun who later becomes the Oba with the title of Oba Ewuare the Great is an epitome of ideal leadership. He rewards deserving citizens for their selfless service. He equally dispenses justice equitably. Emotan is rewarded for her sacrifice and service to Benin kingdom.

EWUARE: Emotan, I mourn for you. You shall become a national deity. The ground on which you will be buried shall be

known as Emotan square. There probably would have been no Benin without your singular sacrifice (93)

This is the hallmark of good leadership. A leadership that rewards its citizens for their patriotism. In the United States of America, Martin Luther King Junior has been posthumously honoured with a National Holiday. Our present leadership in Nigeria should extend this gesture to Late Chief M.K.O Abiola, the symbol of our present democracy process.

Selfless sacrifice in *Emotan* is depicted in Emotan as a woman who puts her life on the line to ensure that justice prevails in Benin kingdom. She refuses to present “ewere leaves” (the leaf of peace) to Oba Uwafiokun during the Ewere festival. This action draws the ire of Oba Uwafiokun.

UWA: Ogbe ma gbaro, Ogba mavbe diaru. (Looking a bit worried)
My chiefs, did you notice that Emotan refused to present her ewere leaves!

ESOGBAN: Your Majesty, keep your mind at rest. We are with you. Who is Emotan? A mere woman who cannot hurt a fly.

IYASE: Your Majesty, that is sabotage. She must be kept under close observation. If she persists, your Ogiawwe can take care of her (21-23)

Emotan is both a follower and a leader who mobilizes the women and gives them a voice in a male – dominated society. Emotan and the women, are the conscience of the kingdom. This brings to fore Wole Soyinka’s submission that “the man dies in all who keep silent in the face of tyranny” (23). In the heydays of Abacha’s tyranny and political maneuvering, Wole Soyinka, late Chief Anthony Enahoro, Late Chief Abraham Adesanya, Late Chief Alex Ekwueme and other pro-democracy activists stood their ground and spoke their resentment of the junta. Late Chief Bola Ige described the five political parties midwifed by Abacha as “the five fingers of a leprous hand.” Our leaders today are a far cry from “fathers” like Abraham Lincoln, Nelson Mandela, Kwame Nkrumah, Julius Nyerere, Uthman Dan Fodio and others. This has been the bane of our development as a nation. Emotan as a leader is able to raise an army to reclaim the throne for Prince Ogun. Faced with the prospect of sacrificing her life in order for Prince Ogun to gain his throne, Emotan says:

EMOTAN: I will lay down my life for the throne of Benin. I will, I will. Difficult though it may be, I have no choice. I am ready to pay the price. Benin will know peace, Benin will know prosperity. and fame (64-65)

Emotan is eulogized as a leader in Act 5 scene 4 in this manner:

ADESUWA: ...You encouraged us to come out of our home and trade at the market... where can we ever find a woman, a leader, a mother, a friend and a fighter like you? (93)

Emotan displayed self sacrifice and selfless service that should ideally accompany true and genuine leadership. This is indeed in consonance with late Ambassador Maitama Sule's assertion that a leader should display "the philosophy of the herdsman". He says the herdsman is ready and prepared to die for his cattle. In like manner, a selfless leader should give his all in service to his fatherland. Patriots like Kwame Nkrumah, Thomas Sankara, Samora Machel, Che Guevara, Amilcar Cabral, Nelson Mandela and others were indeed herdsman who gave their all in service to humanity. Emotan could be referred to as a Martyr for our present leaders to emulate. Selfless service is not assuming an office of responsibility and coming out financially richer than you went in. On the contrary, ideal leadership is a period of stewardship knowing that you are accountable to the people. Adam Oshiomhole, the immediate past governor of Edo State, maintains that:

Leadership is about courage, conviction and being able to act – we need our political leadership to go back to the basics and not the symbolism we currently witness. I think the quality of the Nigerian leadership deteriorated from the days of the military up to the moment that we got our priorities wrong... The way forward is for us, the leaders to go back to the basics and ask ourselves what the issues are... (13)

The Playwright as a Catalyst: Salami as Example.

Countries like France, Russia, China, Burkina Faso, Madagascar, Tunisia and Egypt (Arab spring) and others have gone through hard and turbulent periods or what is generally regarded as people's revolutions in an attempt to correct certain systemic problems (Asigbo and Utoh-Ezeajugh 514). Sadly though, these systemic problems seem to be more prevalent in African and third world countries. These anomalies are engendered by inept leaders who find themselves in the corridors of power yet unprepared for leadership. In their desperation to remain in power, they do all they can to subvert the will of the masses as well as gagging the press. This is what Salami exposes in her play *Emotan*.

Salami as a catalyst uses her dramatic oeuvre to conscientize and galvanized the people to stand against the injustices and bad leadership bedeviling the Nigerian nation. As a catalyst and a vanguard, she deploys her theatre to, not only identify the problems but also hazard possible panacea – the undertaking of a people's revolution as a solution to the ineptitude of our leaders since independence. Corroborating this writer's view on the role of Salami as a catalyst and a vanguard, Emmanuel Dandaura affirms that the:

Playwright is a member of the society, so naturally, his artistic sensibilities are shaped and sharpened by the socio-economic conditions and political happenings of his time (2)

The playwright affects society through his writings because he is not insulated from happenings in his society. The playwright therefore plays the important role of a catalyst in his society using his dramatic oeuvre to sensitize and guide people's reactions to current socio-economic and political happenings. Salami is convinced that the only way out of the dark tunnel of bad leadership is through the hard way. This is why Emotan mobilizes an army to unseat Oba Uwafiokun, the usurper. Emotan equally sacrifices her life to ensure victory and the enthronement of Prince Ogun as the Oba. Salami advocates a mass upheaval to overthrow hoodlums in the garb of leaders that bestride the country's political space. In support of this standpoint, Alex Asigbo in *War of the Tin Gods* says: "Blood is the only sacrifice that can guarantee a brighter future. It is the only sacrifice that can expiate the sins of this nation" (36). From history, playwrights have always felt like Asigbo that "Those who make peaceful change impossible, who remain impervious to the wishes of the opposition, make violent change inevitable" (41-42). Many playwrights have had to cool their heels in various detention facilities for daring to bring up to ridicule the idiosyncrasies of draconian rulers. Nonetheless, contemporary African playwrights have not faltered in using their plays as weapons of conscientization, sensitization and mass mobilization, Wole Soyinka in his *A Play of Giants*, satirizes tyranny and military dictatorships, Femi Osofisan in *Who is Afraid of Solarin* and *Midnight Hotel* lampoons corrupt leadership, Esiaba Irobi in his *Hangmen Also Die* x-rays the issue of embezzlement, Bode Sowande in *Farewell To Babylon* treats bourgeois domination and its resultant backlash – revolt, J. P. Clark in *All for Oil* takes a look at exploitation, Femi Branch, whose stage play titled *Po* performed at Tena Kulture, Victoria Island, Lagos, on the 3rd of September, 2014, exposes the atrocious activities of the political class – leaders, who would do anything to hold on to power to the detriment of the poor masses as well as using the electorate as instruments to achieve their selfish interest (Sam-Duru, 52); Emeka Nwabueze equally signposts a corrupt parliament as the bane of altruistic leadership in *A Parliament of Vultures*.

Conclusion:

Nigerian leaders have over the years found themselves on the lower rung of moral and ethical degeneracy. This is the reason why Nigerian playwrights have consistently taken a swipe at the corruption, ineptitude and follies of our leaders since independence. Playwrights like Salami and others are catalysts yearning for a desired change of the prevailing status quo. These prevailing anomalies leave us with the view that we are not yet out of the tunnel as far as bad leadership is concerned. This prompts this writer to submit that Nigeria as a nation has never had "fathers". This seems to be why we have not made any meaningful progress as a nation since independence. Hence, the timely warning of Dele Sobowale that "the economy of Nigeria will get nowhere until we muscle the big thieves" (7)

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